

Thermodynamic Stabilities of Lanthanides-2-Thiophenylhydrazodimedone Complexes in Dioxane-Water Media

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The thermodynamic parameters for the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes between lanthanide cations and 2-thiophenylhydrazodimedone (2-TPHD) have been determined by potentiometric titrations in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water solution of 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength. The stepwise Gibbs energies of metal complexes varied in the sequence, $\Delta G_1 > \Delta G_2$ and the stepwise enthalpies $\Delta H_1 > \Delta H_2$, and thus the stepwise entropies markedly increase in the order, $\Delta S_1 > \Delta S_2$. The non-linear variation of the thermodynamic parameters of the complex formation has been discussed in terms of differences in the donor ability of dioxane-water solvents.

β -Diketones are well-known chelating agents, capable of forming stable complexes with metal ions. Lanthanide- β -diketones find wide applications¹, including chromatographic separation of the lanthanide series². Azo compound are also used as complexing agents³, and so also the combination of azo compounds and β -diketones⁴.

A reaction between diazonium salt and β -diketone species takes place through the active methylene group to give ligands with chromophoric groups (I) and (II).

The hydrazo structure (II) was substantiated by Yoshihara⁵. The binding characteristics of ligand (II) have been studied. In some cases auxiliary strong coordinating groups such as carboxylate⁶ or hydroxy⁷ or acetyl⁸ have been incorporated. In the present communication the acid-base equilibria and chelating and lanthanide ions chelating tendencies with 2-thiophenylhydrazodimedone (2-TPHD : I) are described. The thermodynamic parameters of the 2-TPHD (I) and its complexes with lanthanide ions are also evaluated.

Results and Discussion

The potentiometric titration curves for ligand metal-ligand systems in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water show that one

proton dissociates from thiophenolic group between $\alpha = 0$ and 1 (where α is the number of moles of base added per mole of ligand present). At higher pH values, one additional proton dissociates from hydrazo group as indicated from the metal-ligand titration curve.

For the general protonation equilibrium,

the constant K_n^H were determined as described earlier⁷. The curves of 2-TPHD in the present lanthanide ions indicate the stepwise formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 type complexes [ML^+ and ML_2^+], where

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE DISSOCIATION REACTIONS OF (2-TPHD) in 75% DIOXANE-WATER

Reaction	$pK_{1,2}^H$				$-\Delta G^a$ kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^b kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^c JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	10°	20°	30°	40°			
$H_2L \rightleftharpoons H^+ + HL^-$	11.38 ± 0.02	10.86 ± 0.03	10.38 ± 0.01	9.91 ± 0.02	3.481	4.954	4.943
$HL^- \rightleftharpoons H^+ + HL$	13.24 ± 0.03	12.67 ± 0.04	12.37 ± 0.02	11.79 ± 0.02	4.100	4.403	1.018

^a±(0.03 - 1.16) kJ mol⁻¹, ^b±(0.03-1.26) JK⁻¹mol⁻¹.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS FOR Ln³⁺-2-TPHD CHELATES IN 75% (v/v) DIOXANE-WATER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Cation	log K ₁ ^a				log K ₂ ^{**}			
	10 ⁰	20 ⁰	30 ⁰	40 ⁰	10 ⁰	20 ⁰	30 ⁰	40 ⁰
H	11.38	10.86	10.38	9.91	13.24	12.67	12.37	11.79
La	13.95	13.13	12.69	12.02	12.34	11.50	11.07	10.38
Ce	14.04	13.29	12.80	12.17	12.36	11.64	11.20	10.58
Pr	14.00	12.21	12.75	12.10	12.35	11.60	11.12	10.50
Nd	14.08	13.30	12.80	12.16	12.45	11.66	11.25	10.56
Sm	14.15	13.40	12.92	12.20	12.53	11.75	11.31	10.63
Eu	14.26	13.47	13.06	12.28	12.61	11.83	11.43	10.71
Gd	13.98	13.17	12.70	12.06	12.39	11.53	11.10	10.40
Tb	14.20	13.42	12.99	12.25	12.55	11.80	11.28	10.70
Dy	14.27	13.49	13.10	12.40	12.70	11.83	11.39	10.80
Hb	14.34	13.56	13.15	12.49	12.77	11.94	11.50	10.89
Er	14.49	13.65	13.24	12.72	12.82	11.97	11.56	10.01
Tm	14.52	13.71	13.37	12.80	12.91	12.10	11.44	11.12
Yb	14.56	13.82	13.40	12.89	13.00	12.18	11.70	11.23
Lu	14.62	13.87	13.55	12.94	13.05	12.28	11.80	11.30

^a±(0.01-0.26), ^{**}±(0.01-0.17).

The stability constants of the formed complexes were calculated from the titration curve using the expressions⁹,

$$\log \bar{n} / (1 - \bar{n}) = \log K_1 - pL \quad (1)$$

$$\log (\bar{n} - 1) / (2 - \bar{n}) = \log K_2 - pL \quad (2)$$

The relations were solved graphically using the plots of $\log [(\bar{n} / (1 - \bar{n}))] \text{ vs } pL$ and $\log (\bar{n} - 1) / (2 - \bar{n}) \text{ vs } pL$. These plots give straight-lines whose intercepts with the pL axis give $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ respectively. The values of the constants were refined using leastsquares method. The values of dissociation constant and thermodynamic parameter are presented in Table 1. Table 2 includes the values of forma-

tion constant. The variations of pK_1^H , pK_2^H , $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ with $1/T$ give straight-lines with correlation coefficients equal to 0.990-0.999. This linear change permits the calculation by the Van't Hoff equation,

$$\log K = -(\Delta H / 2.303RT) + \text{constant} \quad (3)$$

The free energy and entropy change were calculated using the known relationships,

$$-\Delta G = 2.303 RT \log K \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta S = (\Delta H - \Delta G) / T \quad (5)$$

The values of thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR Ln³⁺-2-TPHD CHELATES IN 75% (v/v) DIOXANE-WATER

Cation	-ΔG ₁ kJ mol ⁻¹	-ΔH ₁ ^a kJ mol ⁻¹	-ΔS ₁ ^b kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	-ΔG ₂ kJ mol ⁻¹	-ΔH ₂ ^c kJ mol ⁻¹	-ΔS ₂ ^d kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
La	4.24	5.50	4.24	3.71	5.50	6.03
Ce	4.28	6.16	6.32	3.75	6.05	7.74
Pr	4.26	6.61	7.87	3.73	6.14	8.09
Nd	4.28	6.60	7.80	3.76	6.14	8.00
Sm	4.31	7.16	9.54	3.78	6.16	8.08
Eu	4.35	7.71	11.28	3.81	6.61	9.39
Gd	4.33	6.27	6.79	3.71	6.39	8.97
Tb	4.36	6.83	8.39	3.79	6.61	9.45
Dy	4.38	7.71	11.23	3.82	6.61	9.34
Hb	4.43	8.15	12.62	3.86	7.16	11.08
Er	4.46	8.26	12.85	3.88	7.16	11.00
Tm	4.47	8.48	13.50	3.91	7.38	11.63
Yb	4.50	8.70	14.17	3.94	7.71	12.64
Lu		8.81	14.45	3.97	8.15	14.03

^a±(0.04 -1.12), ^b±(0.04 -1.38), ^c±(0.04 -1.65), ^d±(0.04 -4.12).

The dissociation constants pK_1^H and pK_2^H for 2-TPHD ligand at different temperatures (Table 1) indicate that the neutralisation reactions of the ligand are temperature-dependent. Also, the positive enthalpy values (ΔH_1 and ΔH_2) of the free ligand indicate that the neutralisation reactions of 2-TPHD are an endothermic process, since the ionisation of the ligand is enhanced with increasing temperature. The large positive values of ΔG_1 and ΔG_2 (Table 1) also indicate that the dissociation of 2-TPHD is not spontaneous and a rise in temperature shifts the equilibrium to right, i.e. increasing dissociation of the ligand. On the other hand, the large negative values of ΔG_1 and ΔG_2 (Table 3) in all lanthanide-2-TPHD chelates, indicate that the complex formation reaction proceeds spontaneously.

All the complexes were found to be enthalpy-stabilised. The negative values of ΔH_1 and ΔH_2 (Table 3) for these systems indicate that the complexation reactions are exo-

Fig. 1. Correlation between ΔG_1 and ΔH_1 for Ln^{3+} -2-TPHD complexes in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water.

thermic. The entropy factors ΔS_1 and ΔS_2 for the ligand (Table 1) and its lanthanide complexes (Table 3) have been found to be favourable and agree with the earlier results¹⁰. The plot of ΔG vs ΔH (Fig. 1) for the chelates of lanthanide-2-TPHD shows that there are two lines, one for the lanthanides La-Nd, and the other for the heavier lanthanides Tb-Lu. This is to say that the entropy changes of the reaction will vary regularly for both light and heavy lanthanide series. This accounts for the widespread success of ΔG_1 and ΔH_2 vs third ionisation potential ($3I_p$) graphs (Fig. 2)⁹. It is assumed for simplicity that only bond strength or ΔH° is involved. Since the third ionisation potential may be taken as a rough estimation of the average electron-attracting power of a trivalent metal ion for a source of electrons, such as found in the chelate groups. Hence it is more nearly related to bond energy and ΔH of chelation than of ΔG as

measured by the log of the chelate formation constant. It is also to be noted that ΔH should be more sensitive index of bond strength than ΔG . Fig. 2 shows a plot of $3I_p$ of the gaseous metal against ΔH and ΔG chelation. As can be seen, the relationship is satisfactory, in which the plot of

Fig. 2. Relationship between thermodynamic functions and third ionisation potential for Ln^{3+} -2-TPHD complexes.

ΔG vs $3I_p$ gives roughly two lines for the light and heavier lanthanide ions, while plot of ΔH vs $3I_p$ gives S-shaped curve. This explanation agrees with that obtained earlier¹¹.

As seen in Fig. 3, however, the variation of the thermodynamic quantities as a function of lanthanide atomic number does not give a linear relationship (the curves showed distinct discontinuity between lighter La-Nd and heavier Tb-Lu lanthanides), but showed a general pattern of an early minimum and mid-series maximum (an S-shape or gadolinium break) proceeding from La to Lu.

However, the analogous sequence in ΔH_n and ΔS_n shows the same pattern, which could be related to hydration effects reflected in ΔH and ΔS but not is ΔG (equations 6 and 7),

$$\Delta H_1 = \Delta H_1(\text{g}) - \Delta H(\text{hyd})(\text{L}^-) - \Delta H(\text{hyd})(\text{Ln}^{3+}) + \Delta H(\text{hyd})(\text{LaL}^+) \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta S_1 = \Delta S_1(\text{g}) - \Delta S(\text{hyd})(\text{L}^-) - \Delta S(\text{hyd})(\text{Ln}^{3+}) + \Delta S(\text{hyd})(\text{LnL}^+) \quad (7)$$

As seen in Fig. 3, all of these relations have discontinuities in ΔG_1 , ΔH_1 and ΔS_1 plots near the middle of the lanthanide series. This behaviour is consistent with the model consid-

Fig. 3. Relationship between atomic number and thermodynamic quantities for Ln^{3+} -2-TPHD in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water.

ering different hydration numbers of the lighter (La-Nd) and heavier (Tb-Lu)¹² lanthanides. In this model, La^{3+} to Nd^{3+} were assigned to isostructural series, and Tb^{3+} to Lu^{3+} to another. The hydrated ion in the middle of the series (Sm^{3+} - Tb^{3+}) are assumed either to have structures representing some transition between those of the two major groups or to exist in an equilibrium between the other two structures. The difference in the hydration numbers between light (La-Nd) and heavy (Tb-Lu) lanthanide ions does not exceed unity^{13,14} and it is suggested that lanthanide $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_9^{3+}$ is the possible species for probable species for the light cations and lanthanide $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_9^{3+}$ for the heavier ones. The structural change of hydration sphere of the metal ion near the middle of the lanthanide series will create a compensating effect due to structural change in hydration species of metal ions. If $\Delta H(\text{hyd})(\text{Ln}^{3+})$ and $\Delta H(\text{hyd})(\text{LnL}^+)$ have discontinuities of different magnitudes (equation 6) near the middle of lanthanide series, then the net effect of $\Delta H(\text{hyd})(\text{Ln}^{3+}) + \Delta H(\text{hyd})(\text{LnL}^+)$ is not linear and the curve obtained can be divided into three regions proceeding from La to Lu (Fig. 3). Similar reasoning would apply to the entropies (equation 7). The model of the change in the structure of hydration sphere of the metal ions near the middle of the lanthanide series was supported by other properties besides the thermodynamic ones, which include molal volume^{13,15}, relative viscosity¹⁶, apparent molal heat capacity¹⁷, heat of dilution¹⁸, electrical conductance¹⁴, transition temperature¹⁹, and

Raman stretching bond for Ln^{3+} - OH_2 in glassy solution^{20,21}. Plots of these properties as a function of the lanthanide atomic number or ionic radius showed a general pattern of an early minimum and a mid-series maximum (an S-shaped) proceeding from La to Lu. The entropy values (Table 3) are negative for the studied complex systems. Such negative entropy change can be attributed also to the extensive solvation of metal chelates in aqueous organic medium. The negative stepwise entropy changes observed for 2-TPHD-metal chelate in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water emphasise the predominance of the coordination process. The enthalpy change associated with the complexation reaction is a measure of the difference in the bond energy toward the metal ion between the ligand and the coordinated molecules of solvents. The higher (exothermic) ΔH_b values obtained in all the 2-TPHD-metal chelate could be related to the increase of the solvent basicity, which causes the transfer of metal ion from aqueous dioxane-water to be exothermic as mentioned before²¹.

Fig. 4. Relationship between the stability constants for lanthanide complexes with 2-TPHD and 2-hydroxyphenylhydrazoacetacetanilide (2-HPHAAA) (Ref. 23).

Fig. 3 reveals that the change in ΔG_1 values is very small and then show slight increase for the heavy lanthanides. The deviation from linearity beyond Gd is also noticed in the relation of ΔG_1 (as ΔH_1 and ΔS_1) with atomic number of lanthanide elements (Fig. 3). Anomalies in chelating tendencies of Gd was observed for a wide range of ligands and explained on the basis of solvation sphere through the lanthanide series²¹.

According to Choppin and Graffes²², the lanthanide ions fall into three groups: (i) La to Nd, in which a slowly increasing size of hydration zone could be observed, (ii) Sm to Tb, with a more rapid increase in the size of the hydration sphere with atomic number and (iii) Dy to Lu, in which a large hydration sphere exists. In terms of the enthalpy change on complex formation, the smaller hydration zone about La to Nd should result in a smaller effect than for the Dy to Lu region with an intermediate effect between these two groups. This is precisely the effect observed in Fig. 3. Also, the entropy changes are in agreement with the idea of these three groups of hydrated lanthanide ions.

Finally, from the following discussion, one can prove that the ligand contains three sites of complexation and forming bis-chelates, corroborating our previous work²³. If we consider this the stabilities of the same type ($\log K_{MA}$ or $\log K_{MB}$, where A = 2-TPHD and B = 2-hydroxyphenylhydrazoacetanilide, 2-HPHAAA²³) formed by a similar pair of ligands H_2A and H_2B with a series of lanthanide ions is compared by plotting $\log K_{MA}$ vs $\log K_{MB}$ (Fig. 4). For both types of complexes the plot yields line of equal intercept (0.60) for lanthanide complexes. This suggests that the coordination mode of these ligands towards the series of metal complexes are the same. The value 0.60 of the intercept is expected from the basicity difference ($\sum pK_A^H - \sum pK_B^H$) of the ligands, where $\sum pK_B^H = 23.34$, at 30°, 75% (v/v) dioxane-water and 0.10 M (KNO_3) ionic strength²³. This indicates the validity of the theoretical relationship derived by Irving and Rossotti²⁴ between the logarithms of the stability constants for metal complexes of a similar ligand pair A and B :

$$\log K_{MA} = \log K_{MB} + \log K_{H_2A} - \log K_{H_2B} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 5 shows the correlation between $\log K_1$ and pK^H for Nd^{3+} and Yb^{3+} with a number of 2-carboxy-, 2-hydroxy-

Fig. 5. Relationship between the values of $\log K_1$ for Nd^{III} and Yb^{III} complexes with (1) 2-TPHD, (2) 2-HPHD, (3) 2-CPHD and (4) 2-CPHTTA.

and thiophenyl-hydrizo- β -diketone ligands. The values of $\sum pK^H$ and $\log K_1$ for 2-thiophenylhydrazodimedone (2-TPHD), 2-hydroxyphenylhydrazodimedone (2-HPHD)⁷, 2-carboxyphenylhydrazodimedone (2-CPHD)⁶ and 2-carboxyphenylhydrazothienoyltrifluoroacetone (2-CPHTTA)⁶ were obtained from the reported work. Nd^{3+} and Yb^{3+} were used for this comparison as they represent the average behaviour of the light and heavy lanthanide elements. The correlation (Fig. 5) has been noticed for many metal-ligand systems and it reflects the strongly ionic na-

ture of the bonding of the complexes. Also, this relationship indicates that the studied ligand (2-TPHD) has the tridentate character as the other ligands^{2,4,6} where the coordination sites are sulphur of thiol group, hydrazo nitrogen and ketonic oxygen.

Experimental

The ligand 2-TPHD was prepared by coupling dimedone with diazonium salt of 2-aminothiophenol in an acetate medium²⁵ and the resultant brownish solid was crystallised from ethanol (Found : C, 57.33; H, 6.41; N, 11.06; S, 12.82. Calcd. for : C, 57.14; H, 6.35; N, 11.11; S, 12.70 %).

Stock solutions of lanthanide nitrates were prepared²⁶ from their metal oxides (B.D.H.; 99.9%). Other metal ion solutions were prepared from the corresponding nitrate salt and standardised²⁷. Dioxane was purified by the recommended procedure²⁸. The base used was carbonate-free KOH kept under nitrogen atmosphere and standardised by potassium hydrogen phthalate.

The potentiometric titration was carried out using a WTW'D 8120 Weihen 520 pH-meter fitted with combined glass-calomel electrode. In each run, 30 ml aliquot of the metal-ligand mixture in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water solvent was titrated with standard base. The correction²⁹ for the measured pH values was taken as 0.28. Solutions were adjusted to 0.10 M ionic strength by adding KNO_3 and a constant temperature was maintained with by a thermostat arrangement. Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the solution during the measurement. The titrations were performed at different temperatures, viz. 10, 20, 30, 40°. All titrations were repeated at least twice and the agreement between the pH-readings of the different titrations was usually within ± 0.33 .

References

1. N. AHMED, N. S. BHACCA, J. SERBIN and J. W. WANDER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **93**, 2564.
2. E. W. ERG and J. J. C. ACOSTA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1968, **40**, 101.
3. J. R. KIRBY and R. M. MILBURN, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, **26**, 458.
4. A. G. EVANS, J. C. EVANS, B. A. EL-SHETARY, C. C. ROWLANDS and R. H. MORGAN, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1979, **9**, 19.
5. Y. YOSHIHARA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1963, **36**, 487.
6. A. A. T. RAMADAN, M. S. MOEZ and M. F. EID, *J. Chin. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **33**, 315.
7. A. A. T. RAMADAN, M. S. MOEZ, S. B. EL-MARAGHY and G. A. EL-INANY, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1988, **3**, 125.
8. B. A. EL-SHETARY, S. L. STEFAN, M. S. MOEZ and M. M. MASHAALY, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1988, **66**, 2362.
9. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2940.
10. H. L. KALAR and J. S. MALIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 1427.
11. A. A. RAMADAN, M. S. MOEZ and H. S. SELEM, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1993, **130**, 25.

12. I. GREUTE, *Acta Chim. Scand.*, 1964, **18**, 293.
13. F. H. SPEDDING, M. J. PIKAL and B. O. AYERS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 2440.
14. F. M. SPEDDING, J. A. RARD and V. W. SEAGER, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1974, **19**, 373.
15. F. H. SPEDDING, L. E. SHIERS, M. A. BRAWN, J. L. DEREV, D. L. SWANSON and A. HABENSCHUS, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1975, **20**, 81.
16. F. H. SPEDDING and M. J. PIKAL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 2430.
17. F. H. SPEDDING and K. C. JONES, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 2450.
18. F. H. SPEDDING, D. A. CSEJKA and C. W. DEKOCK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 2423.
19. H. KANNO and Y. AKAMA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1987, **91**, 1263.
20. S. YAMAUCHI, H. KANNO and Y. AKAMA, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1988, **15**, 315.
21. H. KANNO and J. HIRAISHI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, **65**, 574.
22. G. R. CHOPPIN and A. J. GRAFFEO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1961, **65**, 574.
23. B. A. EL-SHETARY, M. S. MOEZ and M. F. EID, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **53**, 679.
24. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1956, **10**, 72.
25. R. ADAMS, "Organic Reactions", Champan and Hall, London, 1959, Vol. 10, p. 59.
26. A. A. T. RAMADAN, M. H. SEADA and E. N. RIZKALLA, *Monatsh Chem.*, 1985, **116**, 463.
27. W. S. WEST, "Complexometry with EDTA and Related Reagents", Broglia Press, London, 1969.
28. J. KUCHARARSKY and L. SAFARIX, "Titration in Non-aqueous Solvents", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1965.
29. H. M. IRVING and U. S. MAHNOT, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1215.